

1 **Toxic Substances Control Act (TSCA) Implementation: How the**
2 **amended law has failed to protect vulnerable populations from toxic**
3 **chemicals in the U.S.**

4

5 Authors:

6 Swati D.G. Rayasam¹

7 Patricia D. Koman²

8 Daniel A. Axelrad³

9 Tracey J. Woodruff^{1,4}

10 Nicholas Chartres^{1*}

11

12 ¹Program on Reproductive Health and the Environment, Department of Obstetrics, Gynecology
13 and Reproductive Sciences, University of California San Francisco School of Medicine, San
14 Francisco, CA 94143 USA

15 ²Environmental Health Sciences, University of Michigan School of Public Health, Ann Arbor, MI
16 48109 USA

17 ³Independent consultant, Washington, DC 20004 USA

18 ⁴Environmental Research and Translation for Health, Department of Obstetrics, Gynecology and
19 Reproductive Sciences, University of California San Francisco School of Medicine, San
20 Francisco, CA 94143 USA

21

22 * Corresponding author: Nicholas.Chartres@ucsf.edu

23

24

25 **Abstract**

26 Exposures to industrial chemicals are widespread and can increase the risk of adverse health
27 effects such as cancer, developmental disorders, respiratory effects, diabetes, and reproductive
28 problems. The amended Toxic Substances Control Act (amended TSCA) requires the U.S.
29 Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) to evaluate risks of chemicals in commerce, account
30 for risk to potentially exposed and susceptible populations, and mitigate risks for chemicals
31 determined to pose an unreasonable risk to human health and the environment. This analysis
32 compares EPA's first 10 chemical risk evaluations under amended TSCA to best scientific
33 practices for conducting risk assessments. We find EPA's risk evaluations underestimated
34 human health risks of chemical exposures by excluding conditions of use and exposure
35 pathways; not considering aggregate exposure and cumulative risk; not identifying all potentially
36 exposed or susceptible subpopulations, and not quantifying differences in risk for susceptible
37 groups; not addressing data gaps; and using flawed systematic review approaches to identify
38 and evaluate the relevant evidence. We present specific recommendations for improving the
39 implementation of amended TSCA using the best available science to ensure equitable, socially
40 just safeguards to public health. Failing to remedy these shortcomings will result in continued
41 systematic underestimation of risk for all chemicals evaluated under amended TSCA.

42 **Keywords:**

43 environmental health; risk assessment; hazard identification; federal policy; susceptibility;
44 environmental justice; health equity

45
46 **Synopsis:**

47 EPA's implementation of amended TSCA didn't incorporate key scientific/methodological
48 factors, underestimating health risks of chemical exposures, particularly to susceptible
49 populations.

50

51 **Graphical Abstract:**

52

53 **Introduction**

54 The 1976 Toxic Substances Control Act (TSCA) was enacted in response to the growing
55 incidence of “environmental disease” caused by the boom in industrial chemical manufacture
56 after World War II.¹ Then U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) Administrator Russell
57 Train called TSCA “one of the most important pieces of 'preventive medicine' legislation" ever
58 passed by Congress.² In 1979, the President’s Toxic Substances Strategy Committee
59 concluded chemicals were a significant source of death and disease in the U.S. and “measured
60 against the need, the handful of chemicals regulated to date have been disappointingly small.”³
61 TSCA remains the primary authority in the U.S. regulating non-pesticide chemicals in
62 commerce.⁴

63 Since 1976, global concerns regarding chemical risks have grown. Recent estimates by
64 the World Health Organization identify two million lives and fifty-three million disability-adjusted-
65 life-years were lost worldwide in 2019 due to chemical exposures.⁵ There is now significantly
66 more evidence on chemical exposures and risks, and increased attention to disproportionate
67 risks to populations near polluting facilities (fenceline communities), children, consumers, and
68 workers.^{6,7}

69 Under 1976 TSCA, chemicals already in commerce were assumed to be safe until
70 shown harmful, and the original law was widely viewed as weak and ineffective.^{4, 8, 9} TSCA
71 provided limited authority to obtain necessary information to assess the risks of chemicals, and
72 imposed significant barriers to regulating chemicals posing substantial risks, even for
73 substances with known harms, such as asbestos.⁸⁻¹³ Various state and local jurisdictions
74 enacted their own chemical laws and regulations to partially fill the gaps left by TSCA.^{14, 15}
75 Increasing market globalization, accumulating scientific evidence of risk, and the growing
76 patchwork of federal, state, and local regulatory requirements eventually set the stage to update
77 TSCA via the Frank Lautenberg Chemical Safety for the 21st Century Act (amended TSCA),
78 enacted in June 2016.¹⁶ In the 40 years between enactment of original TSCA and its 2016
79 amendments, EPA regulated fewer than 10 of over 86,000 existing chemicals registered for use
80 in commerce.^{17,18}

81 Amended TSCA requires EPA to conduct risk evaluations of chemicals in commerce on
82 a specified schedule, consider risks to “potentially exposed or susceptible subpopulations”
83 (PESS), and determine if a chemical poses an “unreasonable risk” without consideration of
84 cost.¹⁹ It also requires EPA to regulate any existing chemical determined to pose an
85 unreasonable risk “to the extent necessary so that the chemical substance no longer presents
86 such risk.”¹⁹ Finally, it requires EPA to “use scientific information, technical procedures,
87 measures, methods, protocols, methodologies, or models, employed in a manner consistent
88 with the best available science.”¹⁹

89 However, the amended law is missing aspects of its regulatory contemporaries in the
90 generation and use of scientific data. Unlike the European Union’s Registration, Evaluation,
91 Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH), amended TSCA still places the burden of
92 obtaining the necessary data to evaluate existing chemicals on EPA rather than
93 manufacturers.²⁰ Amended TSCA also lacks important scientific principles found in the Food
94 Quality Protection Act (FQPA) of 1996, including requirements for EPA to apply adjustment

95 factors to account for early life susceptibility and calculate aggregate exposure and cumulative
96 risk.²¹ Further, amended TSCA preempts some state action and concentrates authority at the
97 federal level barring some exceptions (such as California’s Proposition 65).¹⁵ (see Supporting
98 Information, Section 1) This leaves many critical implementation decisions with EPA, including
99 how to assess and apply the available science, making it vulnerable to political interference and
100 scientific integrity concerns.²²⁻²⁴ The weaknesses in amended TSCA could be improved by
101 health-protective implementation of EPA’s existing authorities. The stakes are high, as
102 widespread use of industrial chemicals, many of which can cross the placental barrier, has led
103 to generations of children being born pre-polluted.^{16, 25}

104 How EPA utilizes science to implement amended TSCA is important to population
105 health, particularly to PESS. In this analysis, we compare EPA’s first 10 chemical risk
106 evaluations completed under amended TSCA between June 2020 and January 2021 (referred
107 to as the “first 10”) to the “best available science” to evaluate risks to public health from
108 chemicals in commerce.²⁶ The first 10 chemicals are: Asbestos, 1-Bromopropane (1-BP),
109 Carbon Tetrachloride, C.I. Pigment Violet 29 (PV29), Hexabromocyclododecane (HBCD), 1,4-
110 Dioxane, Methylene Chloride, N-Methylpyrrolidone (NMP), Perchloroethylene (PCE), and
111 Trichloroethylene (TCE).

112 We first present an overview of key provisions in TSCA regarding prioritization and risk
113 evaluation. We then review EPA’s approach to several elements common to all TSCA risk
114 evaluations:

- 115 • Conditions of use and exposure pathways,
- 116 • Aggregate exposure and cumulative risk,
- 117 • Potentially exposed or susceptible subpopulations (PESS),
- 118 • Data gaps, and
- 119 • Systematic review.

120 We selected these topics based on our previous studies and their importance to estimation of
121 risk.^{11, 27} For each element we discuss (1) what is required under amended TSCA, (2) how EPA
122 implemented these requirements during the first 10 risk evaluations, (3) the public health
123 implications of EPA's implementation, and (4) our recommendations if the element is
124 scientifically inadequate. This paper does not cover all the issues with the first 10 risk
125 evaluations, but other manuscripts discuss additional critical issues including using health-
126 protective adjustment (uncertainty) factors for risk characterization and a unified approach to
127 dose-response assessment.²⁸⁻³⁰

128

129 [Overview of the TSCA risk evaluation process](#)

130 Under amended TSCA, EPA must develop processes to evaluate and address risks to
131 human health and the environment from 'New Chemicals' (chemicals not yet on the market) and
132 'Existing Chemicals' (chemicals currently on the market in the U.S.) (see Supporting
133 Information, Section 2, Figure S1). This analysis focuses on EPA's existing chemicals risk
134 evaluations.

135 Amended TSCA requires EPA create a process designating existing chemicals as either
136 "high-priority" (requiring risk evaluation) or "low-priority" substances (risk evaluations not
137 currently required) (see Supporting Information, Section 2, Figure S2).

138 Amended TSCA requires EPA take two initial actions to evaluate the first set of existing
139 chemicals. First, EPA had to select 10 existing chemicals for evaluation by December 2016 and
140 complete those evaluations by June 2020. Second, EPA was required to issue final "framework"
141 rules outlining its approach for chemical prioritization and risk evaluation by June 2017. The
142 framework rules were proposed in January 2017 by the Obama-Biden EPA but finalized in July
143 2017 by the Trump-Pence EPA. Some deficits in EPA's risk evaluations described below are a
144 result of changes between proposed and final versions of the framework rules; relevant changes
145 are outlined in Supporting Information, Section 3.

146
147
148
149
150
151
152
153
154
155
156
157
158
159
160
161
162
163
164
165
166
167

Conditions of use and exposure pathways

Defining how chemicals are used and pathways is a key component to identifying exposures and risks.

What is required under amended TSCA

The law outlines several requirements for the contents of a risk evaluation (Supporting Information, Section 1). EPA must:

integrate and assess available information on hazards and exposures for the conditions of use of the chemical substance. §2605(b)(4)(F)(i)

take into account, where relevant, the likely duration, intensity, frequency, and number of exposures under the conditions of use of the chemical substance. §2605(b)(4)(F)(iv)

'conditions of use' means the circumstances...under which a chemical substance is intended, known, or reasonably foreseen to be manufactured, processed, distributed in commerce, used, or disposed of. §2602(4)

Taken together, these passages require EPA comprehensively assess conditions of use and exposures pathways in its risk evaluations; affirmed by a 2019 appeals court ruling.^{31, 32} The only statutory exclusions are for certain uses regulated under other statutes, such as pesticides, tobacco products, food additives, and cosmetics.

168 [How EPA implemented these requirements](#)

169 EPA's first 10 risk evaluations addressed exposures from a broad range of conditions of
170 use through multiple exposure pathways; however, the Agency excluded several aspects of
171 exposure based primarily on two inappropriate rationales.

172 1. EPA asserted it could choose which conditions of use to include in each risk
173 evaluation. In its final risk evaluation framework rule, EPA claimed it could exclude
174 certain uses, asserting broad discretion to select conditions of use to assess "for
175 each chemical substance on a case-by-case basis...consistent with the objective of
176 conducting a technically sound, manageable evaluation."³³

177 This claim of discretion to exclude conditions of use substantially affected the scope of three out
178 of the first 10 risk evaluations: asbestos, carbon tetrachloride, and 1,4-dioxane (see Supporting
179 Information, Section 2, Table S1). For example, EPA's final "Asbestos Part 1" considers only
180 current uses, excluding on-going exposures from legacy uses (e.g., past uses of asbestos, as in
181 automotive brakes or housing materials, that can result in current exposure) and associated
182 disposal.

183 2. EPA limited the exposures considered in risk evaluation by interpreting TSCA as only
184 considering chemical exposures not addressed by other environmental statutes,
185 rather than a comprehensive chemical risk reduction tool. In May 2018, EPA issued
186 problem formulation documents for each TSCA risk evaluation saying EPA would:

187 "focus its analytical efforts on exposures that are likely to present the
188 greatest concern and consequently merit a risk evaluation under TSCA,
189 by excluding, on a case-by-case basis, certain exposure pathways that
190 fall under the jurisdiction of other EPA-administered statutes."³⁴

191

192 EPA's decision to narrowly limit exposure pathways considered under TSCA had a substantial
193 impact on the first 10 risk evaluations. In eight, the Agency did not assess three or more
194 exposure pathways such as ambient air, disposal, or drinking water, based on the rationale of
195 being addressed by other statutes like the Clean Air Act (CAA), Safe Drinking Water Act
196 (SDWA), or Clean Water Act (CWA) (Supporting Information, Section 2, Table S2).

197

198 Implications for public health

199 EPA's exclusions of conditions of use in three of the first 10 risk evaluations and exposure
200 pathways in eight of the first 10 mean these evaluations systematically underestimated
201 exposure and risk. The logic of assuming that coverage by another statute results in sufficient
202 risk reductions is flawed as it requires EPA to assume equal levels of protection from different
203 statutes. Although other statutes such as the CAA and SDWA may have some overlapping
204 jurisdiction, they do not necessarily meet the health-protective standards required by amended
205 TSCA. Under CAA, EPA evaluates residual risk for chemicals specified as hazardous air
206 pollutants (HAPs) following implementation of technology-based standards. However, these
207 residual risk analyses have gaps and limitations, for example EPA is not required to consider
208 risks of combined emissions from different industries to fence-line communities. The reduction of
209 some chemicals under other statutes can result in regrettable substitutions and outcomes which
210 may be less health-protective than TSCA.³⁵ For example, EPA's Regulatory Impact Analysis
211 (RIA) for reductions of Hydrofluorocarbons (HFCs) under the American Innovation and
212 Manufacturing Act of 2020 (AIM Act) documented that increased production of
213 Hydrofluoroolefins (HFOs), expected to substitute for HFCs could increase carbon tetrachloride
214 emissions. Deferring risk management of these emissions to other statutory authorities which,
215 unlike TSCA, don't contain explicit language to consider risks to PESS could result in increased
216 risks in communities already experiencing elevated respiratory and cancer risks.³⁶

217 EPA's exclusions also involved instances where a chemical was not regulated, even
218 though it was within jurisdiction of another statute, which is inconsistent with EPA's justification
219 for exclusion. For example, EPA's 1-bromopropane risk evaluation, finalized in August 2020, did
220 not assess the ambient air pathway, even though 1-bromopropane was not listed as a HAP until
221 January 2022, and any new or revised CAA standards for industry sectors emitting 1-
222 bromopropane may not be established for several years.³⁷ EPA estimates 1-bromopropane is in
223 widespread use, with annual 2007 emissions of 20,000 to 30,000 metric tons and with a growth
224 rate of up to 20%/year in the U.S.³⁸ EPA's 1,4-dioxane risk evaluation similarly excluded the
225 drinking water pathway, even though under the SWDA, EPA has not established a National
226 Primary Drinking Water Regulation for 1,4-dioxane or even decided whether one is necessary.
227 Almost 30 million people in the U.S. receive drinking water with 1,4-dioxane levels above the
228 reference concentration of 0.35 µg/L.³⁹

229 TSCA, unlike other statutes, offers the opportunity for primary prevention (eliminating risk at the
230 source), which can be more effective than regulatory tools available under other statutes and
231 has been promoted as an EPA strategy since the 1990s.^{40, 41} For example, it may be more
232 effective and less costly to use TSCA to prevent releases of certain chemicals (such as 1,4-
233 dioxane) to water, rather than trying to use the SDWA and CWA to address water contamination
234 after the fact. EPA can only determine whether regulations under other statutes are sufficient to
235 meet TSCA's "unreasonable risk" determination by assessing all conditions of use and exposure
236 pathways in the risk evaluation first. In addition even when exposures are within jurisdiction of
237 other statutes they may be important contributors to aggregate exposures (see discussion
238 below in *Aggregate Exposure and Cumulative Risk*) and affect the determination of whether or
239 not a chemical poses an unreasonable risk.

240 EPA's exclusion of conditions of use and exposure pathways from risk evaluations may
241 pose disproportionate risks to PESS. For example, communities near manufacturing facilities
242 and contaminated sites are often those with lower wealth, poorer health, and with a majority of

243 residents who are people of color.⁴²⁻⁴⁴ Chemical exposures from industry emissions to air and
244 releases to water frequently result in disproportionate exposures to these communities, even
245 after accounting for regulatory controls under other statutes, particularly as communities of color
246 are more likely to have water systems with repeat violations under the SDWA and thus higher
247 exposures.^{45,46, 47} As TSCA has an explicit charge to consider PESS (discussed below), it is
248 important to consider conditions of use and exposure pathways posing risks to over-burdened
249 communities, as it allows EPA to make informed decisions about how to best regulate.

250

251 Recommendations for Change

252 EPA should revise its first 10 risk evaluations to incorporate all conditions of use and
253 include exposure pathways within the jurisdiction of other EPA statutes and continue to do so in
254 future risk evaluations.

255 In June 2021, EPA announced it would conduct further analysis of at least some of the
256 excluded exposure pathways for seven of the first 10 chemicals, and it would also revisit the
257 excluded 1,4-dioxane byproduct conditions of use. In January 2022, EPA released a draft
258 “screening level methodology” for assessing the air and water pathways.⁴⁴ Following completion
259 of this methodology, EPA will consider whether to revise or supplement the risk evaluations to
260 account for currently excluded exposure pathways.

261

262 Aggregate Exposure and Cumulative Risk

263 Failure to assess aggregate exposure and cumulative risk results in evaluations that
264 understate exposure and risk. In 2022 EPA issued its Equity Action Plan, highlighting a
265 commitment to addressing cumulative impacts across its programs.⁴⁸ EPA has assessed
266 aggregate exposure and cumulative risk of pesticides as required by the 1996 Food Quality
267 Protection Act, but it has rarely done such analyses of industrial chemicals under TSCA.²¹

268

269 What is required under amended TSCA

270 When conducting a risk evaluation, amended TSCA requires EPA (Supporting
271 Information, Section 1):

272 describe whether aggregate or sentinel exposures to a chemical substance under the
273 conditions of use were considered, and the basis for that consideration. §2605

274 (b)(4)(F)(ii)

275

276 Amended TSCA also requires EPA to eliminate the unreasonable risk posed by a
277 chemical substance from:

278 the manufacture, processing, distribution in commerce, use, or disposal of a chemical
279 substance or mixture, or any combination of such activities. §2605 (d)(3)(A)(i)(I)

280

281 EPA defines aggregate exposure as “the combined exposures to an individual from a single
282 chemical substance across multiple routes and across multiple pathways,”³³ and cumulative risk
283 assessment as the “analysis, characterization, and possible quantification of the combined risks
284 to health or the environment from multiple agents or stressors,” considering both chemical and
285 non-chemical stressors.⁴⁹ Non-chemical stressors include biological and physical agents (e.g.,
286 pathogens), psychosocial stressors (e.g., exposure to fatal police violence), and health or
287 disease status (e.g., diabetes).

288

289 How EPA implemented these requirements

290 EPA, to a limited extent, considered aggregate exposure in two of the first 10 risk
291 evaluations. For NMP, EPA aggregated dermal and inhalation exposure using a
292 pharmacokinetic model but did not consider combined uses or exposure settings (e.g., both at

293 work and at home).⁵⁰ For HBCD, EPA aggregated general population exposures to
 294 environmental media using population biomonitoring data.⁵¹ In the remaining eight risk
 295 evaluations, EPA considered sentinel rather than aggregate exposures due to concerns about
 296 “overestimating” risk, as detailed below.⁵² EPA assessed three exposed populations separately:
 297 workers exposed directly or indirectly; consumers exposed via products; and the general
 298 population exposed via ambient air and drinking water. However, EPA assessed inhalation and
 299 dermal exposures separately for workers, without calculating combined exposure for workers
 300 exposed via both routes. EPA also assessed consumer exposures for individual products
 301 without calculating the combined exposure for consumers using multiple products containing the
 302 same chemical. Finally, EPA did not aggregate the exposures of individuals who have
 303 occupational, consumer, and general population exposures – such as individuals exposed at
 304 both work and home (Figure 1).

305
 306 Figure 1. An example of aggregate and cumulative exposure to chemicals and non-chemical stressors across sources
 307 and populations compared to the current EPA approach. Though not shown, within these exposure pathways, EPA
 308 separated individual consumer or commercial product uses by product type and separated workers and what EPA refers
 309 to as occupational non-users (those in the workplace exposed but not using the chemical under evaluation). The figures in
 310 grey represent the pathways that EPA has yet to implement under amended TSCA.

311
312
313
314
315
316
317
318
319
320
321
322
323
324
325
326
327
328
329
330
331
332
333
334
335
336

EPA did not conduct cumulative risk assessments in the first 10 risk evaluations, preventing consideration of how chemical exposure risks may be amplified by co-exposure to other chemicals contributing to common adverse outcomes or to non-chemical stressors, such as anti-blackness or xenophobia, exacerbating the risk of adverse outcomes from chemical exposures.^{53, 54}

Implications for public health

In the US, more than 130 million people reside in “vulnerability zones” surrounding one or more of the 3,433 facilities producing, storing, and using highly toxic chemicals, the majority of which are Black or Latino and with higher rates of poverty.⁵⁵ These communities have not been adequately protected from environmental harms, with even the most fundamental protections afforded under the law.⁵⁶⁻⁵⁸

EPA’s choice to consider sentinel and not aggregate exposures underestimated risk in the first 10 risk evaluations, as we illustrate using 1,4-dioxane. A worker may inhale and be dermally exposed to a 1,4-dioxane solvent during their shift and exposed at home through multiple consumer products, such as all-purpose cleaners containing 1,4-dioxane. However, EPA calculated worker risks separately for inhalation and dermal exposures and separately for each consumer product; without considering the exposure of workers who are also consumers. This worker may also live near their workplace, a factory releasing 1,4-dioxane into the air and drinking water, but EPA’s risk evaluation did not consider drinking water or ambient air exposures (see exposure pathways above, and Supporting Information, Section 2, Table S2). A complete aggregate exposure assessment would account for individuals who experience combinations of inhalation and dermal exposure at work, contact with multiple consumer products at work or home, and are exposed to contaminated air or drinking water in their communities. EPA indicated that “Using an additive approach to aggregate exposure and risk in

337 this case would result in an overestimate of risk” without providing evidence to support this
338 assertion.⁵² EPA’s concern about overestimation of risk led to the Agency addressing exposures
339 independently, resulting in underestimation of risk to individuals exposed via multiple pathways,
340 multiple settings, and multiple conditions of use (Figure 1); failing to meet its mandate to protect
341 public health and in particular PESS who disproportionately experience these overlapping
342 exposures.

343 Not considering cumulative risk also underestimates risk.^{59, 60} For example, using
344 publicly available data from the U.S. EPA Toxics Release Inventory (TRI), researchers were
345 able to establish counties throughout the US reporting air emissions of various chemicals linked
346 to respiratory cancer, including formaldehyde, a leukemogen. Nineteen counties were identified
347 with a total of 10 or more respiratory carcinogens being reported (including formaldehyde) and
348 an analysis of the demographic characteristics of these counties found correlations between the
349 number of facilities releasing formaldehyde air emissions and speaking English “less than well,”
350 living in a single-parent household, living in a mobile home, living in multi-unit housing, or
351 identifying as disabled.⁶¹ By only examining the risk of an adverse outcome from exposure to a
352 single chemical, EPA overlooked how multiple exposures (chemical and non-chemical) may
353 combine to produce a common adverse health outcome. (Figure 1).

354

355 Recommendations for Change

356 Only amended TSCA provides the ability to aggregate exposure of a single chemical
357 across all sources, uses, pathways and exposure settings to determine whether it poses an
358 unreasonable risk. Using the best available science, as required by TSCA, means EPA must
359 quantify the aggregate exposures and cumulative risks.^{53, 54}

360 EPA should combine quantitative exposure estimates across exposure pathways and settings
361 (Figure 1), including chemical uses not subject to TSCA such as food packaging, and assess
362 the impacts of exposure to multiple chemical mixtures and structural drivers of health.^{53 25, 54, 62}
363 This approach is in line with existing EPA guidance, approaches recommended by authoritative
364 bodies such as the National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine (NASEM), and
365 an executive order from President Biden.^{53,54,49,63, 64}

366 In January 2022, EPA released a draft screening level methodology to assess air and
367 water exposure pathways for the general population living near facilities reporting through the
368 Toxic Release Inventory.⁴⁴ Although EPA specifically states the case studies are not meant as
369 aggregate or cumulative exposure or risk frameworks, the techniques could be adapted for
370 such.

371 EPA should acquire the data necessary to conduct aggregate and cumulative
372 assessments by using TSCA's data gathering and testing authorities (see section *Data Gaps*
373 below). To facilitate timely risk evaluations, EPA should utilize health-protective adjustment
374 factors while more specific data are under development.²⁸⁻³⁰

375

376 Potentially Exposed or Susceptible Subpopulations (PESS)

377 Exposures to toxic chemicals disproportionately impact the health of, such as children,
378 low-wealth communities, and communities of color.^{16, 65-67} Failure to identify all PESS and
379 account for quantitative differences in risk of susceptible subpopulations results in
380 underestimation of risk.

381

382 What is required under amended TSCA

383 Under amended TSCA, EPA is mandated to (Supporting Information, Section 1):

384 determine whether a chemical substance presents an unreasonable risk of injury to health
385 or the environment, without consideration of costs or other nonrisk factors, including an
386 unreasonable risk to a potentially exposed or susceptible subpopulation...§2605(b)(4)(A)

387 PESS is defined as:

388 a group of individuals within the general population identified by the Administrator who,
389 due to either greater susceptibility or greater exposure, may be at greater risk than the
390 general population of adverse health effects from exposure to a chemical substance or
391 mixture, such as infants, children, pregnant women, workers, or the elderly. §2602(12)

392

393 How EPA implemented these requirements

394 In its proposed risk evaluation framework rule, EPA's definition of PESS elaborated on the
395 statutory definition to better capture intrinsic and extrinsic factors affecting susceptibility:

396 Potentially exposed or susceptible subpopulation means a group of individuals within the
397 general population identified by the Agency who, due to either greater susceptibility or
398 greater exposure, may be at greater risk than the general population of adverse health
399 effects from exposure to a chemical substance or mixture, including but not limited to,
400 infants, children, pregnant women, workers, or the elderly. EPA may identify a
401 susceptible subpopulation in an individual risk evaluation upon consideration of various
402 intrinsic (e.g., life stage, reproductive status, age, gender, genetic traits) or acquired
403 (e.g., pre-existing disease, geography, workplace) characteristics that may affect
404 exposure or modify the risk of illness or disease.⁶⁸

405

406 In the final risk evaluation framework rule, EPA did not use the language from the
407 proposed rule and instead used the text of the statute (see above) without elaboration.³³ This
408 definition does not explicitly identify the full range of intrinsic and extrinsic factors influencing the
409 health impacts of chemical exposures.

410 EPA's approach and terminology to identify PESS varied considerably in the first 10 risk
411 evaluations. Among the inconsistencies are differences in whether health conditions related to a
412 chemical's hazards were considered and whether fence-line communities were included, as
413 detailed below and by other experts.²⁸ Additionally, EPA's language regarding PESS is vague,
414 in some cases discussing general factors that may increase susceptibility (e.g., alcohol
415 consumption, nutrition, genetic differences) without clearly identifying groups as PESS. In
416 several instances, groups named as PESS in the statute were not identified in the risk
417 evaluations; for example, pregnant and aging populations were not considered PESS for 1,4-
418 dioxane and PV-29. Supporting Information, Section 2, Table S3 illustrates the range of
419 approaches and deficiencies in identifying PESS for four of the first 10 chemical risk
420 evaluations.

421 While EPA's approaches to identifying PESS varied, its approaches to quantifying PESS
422 risks were consistent. For PESS identified based on elevated exposure, EPA's used "high-end"
423 estimates of exposure for each condition of use and exposure pathway in calculating risks. EPA
424 said these high-end estimates, which do not consider aggregate exposures, satisfied its
425 statutory requirement regarding sentinel exposures (see Aggregate/Cumulative section above).
426 For PESS identified as having elevated susceptibility, EPA did not adjust its risk calculations,
427 saying it lacked "sufficient quantitative information about these potential sources of
428 susceptibility."⁶⁹ EPA used a 10-fold adjustment factor to account for human variability, noting
429 uncertainty regarding whether it was sufficient to account for differences in risk of susceptible
430 subpopulations. However, lack of data does not equate to lack of hazard or risk.²⁷

431
432 **Implications for public health**
433 Scientific evidence demonstrates intrinsic (e.g., age, pre-existing disease, reproductive status,
434 genetics) and extrinsic factors (e.g., stress, racism, poverty, and
435 geographic/socioeconomic/cultural/workplace factors) can increase exposures and susceptibility

436 to environmental chemical exposure risks as well as adverse health outcomes.⁷⁰⁻⁷⁴ Communities
437 of color disproportionately bear the burden of adverse health impacts from chemical exposures
438 (detailed above). Compared to white non-Hispanic children, Black children are more likely to be
439 diagnosed with asthma (14% v. 6.5%) and learning disabilities (10.2% v. 7.9%); and Black
440 women are more likely to experience pre-term birth compared to white non-Hispanic women
441 (14% v. 9.2%).⁷⁵ Compared to white non-Hispanic children, Latino children are more likely to be
442 diagnosed with obesity (24% v. 14%) and Puerto Rican children are more likely to be diagnosed
443 with autism (4.6% v. 2.9%).⁷⁵ Contrary to the direction of amended TSCA, EPA did not take a
444 comprehensive and consistent approach to identifying or considering PESS in the first 10 risk
445 evaluations and omitted PESS identified in the statute; ultimately leading EPA to underestimate
446 risk. For identified PESS, EPA did not apply approaches ensuring elevated exposures and risks
447 of these populations were completely accounted for.

448 The 1-bromopropane risk evaluation is an example of EPA's limited approach to
449 quantifying risks to PESS. EPA identified a single exposure to this dry cleaning chemical during
450 a critical window of fetal development may be sufficient to produce adverse developmental
451 effects.³⁷ However, it "did not calculate risk for children associated with acute exposure at dry
452 cleaners because the acute health domains (developmental effects) are not applicable to
453 children."³⁷ Further, EPA did not calculate risks for chronic exposure for children at dry cleaners
454 because "EPA believes exposure to children at workplaces are unlikely to be chronic in
455 nature."³⁷ EPA's risk evaluation assumes exposures to children happen only in a four-hour
456 period after school, likely inaccurate for school-age children and younger who may spend the
457 majority of their time in family-owned dry-cleaning facilities.⁷⁶

458
459 EPA generally accounted for differential dose-response in identified PESS throughout the risk
460 evaluations by assuming the typical 10-fold factor to account for human variability was sufficient

461 to account for any differences. EPA applied this default without evaluating its sufficiency, and
462 despite contrary evidence, overall underestimating risk to PESS.^{29, 53}

463

464 Recommendations for Change

465 EPA should explicitly name parameters qualifying populations as susceptible to ensure
466 its risk evaluations assess whether each chemical poses an unreasonable risk to PESS. EPA
467 should use a modified version of the PESS definition from its 2017 proposed TSCA risk
468 evaluation framework rule, explicitly identifying extrinsic factors:

469 Potentially susceptible subpopulation means a group of individuals or
470 communities within the general population identified by the Agency who, due to greater
471 susceptibility may be at greater risk than the general population of adverse health effects
472 from exposure to a chemical substance or mixture, including but not limited to infants,
473 children, pregnant women, workers, or aging populations. Susceptibility can be due to
474 both intrinsic (e.g., pre-existing disease, life stage, reproductive status, age, sex, genetic
475 traits) and extrinsic (e.g., food insecurity, geography, socioeconomic status,
476 racism/discrimination, cultural, workplace) factors when identifying this population.

477 EPA should prepare a comprehensive methodology to identify PESS and quantify their risks
478 consistently within and across the TSCA risk evaluations; it has taken this approach in
479 identifying at-risk populations under the Clean Air Act and the NASEM identified this as a
480 goal.^{77, 78} Studies by community groups such as the impacts of the Deepwater Horizon oil
481 disaster on fishing communities, the quantification of heavy metals in water used by Native
482 American tribes the consumption of fish by tribal populations in heavily polluted areas, and air
483 pollution in Detroit can be used as guides.⁷⁹⁻⁸²

484 EPA should use its data gathering authorities (below) and quantify the exposure and risks to all
485 PESS, and as data are being developed, EPA should utilize health-protective defaults to
486 account for elevated exposures and susceptibility where specific data are lacking, as

487 recommended by the NASEM.⁵³ Data and methods are available for improved treatment of
488 human variability, including probabilistic methods, in cases where chemical-specific data are
489 unavailable.^{29, 30, 53, 83, 84}

490

491 Data Gaps

492 The data underpinning risk evaluations must be extensive, multi-disciplinary, and
493 sufficient to quantify all relevant hazard endpoints; failure to do so will understate exposure
494 levels and underestimate risk, particularly for PESS.

495

496 What is required under amended TSCA

497 Amended TSCA states EPA has broad authority to collect relevant information for the
498 identification, prioritization, risk evaluation, and risk management processes (Supporting
499 Information, Section 1). It is required the Administrator:

500 take into consideration information relating to a chemical substance or mixture,
501 including hazard and exposure information, under the conditions of use, that is
502 reasonably available to the Administrator (§ 2625(k)).

503

504 Reasonably available information is defined as:

505 information that EPA possesses or can reasonably generate, obtain and synthesize for
506 use, considering the deadlines specified in 15 U.S.C. 2605(b) for prioritization and risk
507 evaluation.³³

508

509 EPA has various tools to obtain the data for a comprehensive risk evaluation, including
510 TSCA section 8 which authorizes EPA to require manufacturers and processors to: submit
511 reports to EPA containing the volume of the chemical manufactured or processed, the

512 conditions of use and the hazard and exposure potential (§ 2607(a)); submit any records of
513 significant adverse reactions to health or the environment alleged to have been caused by the
514 substance or mixture (§ 2607(c)); and submit unpublished health and safety studies (§ 2607(d)).
515

516 When EPA lacks necessary information to perform a risk evaluation, the Administrator
517 may use TSCA section 4 to:

518 require the development of new information relating to a chemical substance or mixture
519 if the Administrator determines that the information is necessary to...perform a risk
520 evaluation under section 2605(b) of this title (§ 2603(a)(2)(A)(i)).
521

522 Under amended TSCA, EPA can use its section 8 reporting authorities (§2607) and section 4
523 testing authority (§2603) to require chemical manufacturers to provide the data, including
524 conducting new health effects studies of chemicals, necessary to perform a risk evaluation.
525

526 [How EPA implemented these requirements](#)

527 EPA did not issue any section 4 test orders for toxicity information for the first 10
528 chemical risk evaluations, despite several chemicals, such as C. I. Pigment Violet 29 (PV29),
529 lacking necessary information on critical health endpoints.⁸⁵ In conducting the first 10 risk
530 evaluations EPA only used its section 4 authority to issue test orders for PV29, and those test
531 orders were limited to solubility testing and occupational exposure monitoring, without requiring
532 any health effects studies.⁸⁵
533

534 [Implications for public health](#)

535 EPA must have sufficient data on health effects and exposures to conduct a
536 comprehensive risk evaluation. However, in several instances, EPA determined conditions of

537 use of the first 10 chemicals evaluated under amended TSCA did not present an unreasonable
538 risk without sufficient information. Peer reviewers in EPA's Science Advisory Committee on
539 Chemicals (SACC) identified multiple instances of inadequate information, such as "large data
540 gaps that preclude coming to confident conclusions regarding certain subpopulations" (PV29)
541 and "The information used to evaluate worker exposure was generally lacking in its ability to
542 present a coherent picture of this critical element of risk" (1,4-dioxane).⁸⁶

543 EPA did not address critical data gaps even after they were identified in peer review. For
544 example, the SACC found "insufficient data to assess the potential neurotoxicity of 1,4-
545 Dioxane...[or] to assess the toxicity of 1,4-Dioxane on other non-cancer outcomes such as
546 immunotoxicity."³⁷ EPA did not use its statutory authorities to obtain data to assess these
547 outcomes, preventing them from being considered in the final risk evaluation.

548 Where there was scant data, EPA failed to account for limitations and inappropriately
549 drew conclusions about health effects. For example, EPA determined PV29 was not a
550 reproductive or developmental hazard based on a study conducted using guideline OECD 421.
551 However, the OECD 421 test protocol and EPA's risk assessment guidelines clearly establish
552 OECD 421 alone cannot show a chemical is not a reproductive or developmental toxicant, and
553 additional data are needed to establish a chemical lacks reproductive/developmental toxicity.
554 Instead, EPA disregarded the test protocol's established limitations and concluded PV29 did not
555 cause reproductive toxicity, as "EPA believes that OECD 421 is adequate to determine whether
556 additional reproductive testing is necessary. As no significant adverse effects were observed in
557 the study, EPA believes that this provides justification that no additional reproductive testing is
558 necessary."⁸⁷ Without further testing, however, EPA's conclusion PV29's reproductive or
559 developmental toxicity is invalid and does not represent the best available science.

560

561 Recommendations for Change

562 EPA must apply its reporting and testing authorities under amended TSCA to require chemical
563 manufacturers to provide the data, including toxicity studies, necessary to perform its ongoing
564 and future risk evaluations (Supporting Information, Section 1). EPA must also implement
565 approaches to incentivize and require manufacturers to provide appropriate and independent
566 data. It is critical EPA increase transparency by reevaluating the confidential
567 business information (CBI) claims allowing industry to shield critical data from public view; more
568 than 50,000 chemicals worldwide have been registered for use without disclosing their
569 identities.⁸⁸ Second, EPA should derive provisional toxicity values, applying multiple default
570 adjustment factors as needed to account for any lack of data, as recommended by authoritative
571 bodies such as the NASEM.^{53, 89-93}

572 Third, application of “New Approach Methods” (NAMs) has been proposed to facilitate
573 the number of hazard evaluations EPA can complete, while replacing the need for animal
574 testing and reducing costs.^{94, 95} While there is potential for these tools to provide more timely
575 information on hazards of concern, thus reducing the time between potential human exposure
576 and action to mitigate these harms, NAMs also have well established limitations, including limits
577 to their ability to identify chronic and systemic health endpoints such as immunotoxicity,
578 endocrine effects and developmental neurotoxicity.⁹⁶⁻⁹⁸

579 These limitations have led the U.S. EPA Children’s Health Protection Advisory
580 Committee (CHPAC) to warn in a recent report “cell-based assays and other high-throughput
581 toxicity tests, often called New Approach Methods (NAMs), have the potential to provide needed
582 data and could be used to establish potential hazards or upgrade overall hazard identification.
583 However, due to important limitations, data from NAMs cannot be used to rule-out a specific
584 hazard”.⁹⁹ EPA should instead use NAMs to provide “actionable evidence,” or a scientific basis

585 for health protective actions, as recommended by regulatory agencies such as California
586 EPA.¹⁰⁰

587 Amended TSCA requires EPA to complete priority designations no more than 12 months
588 after formally initiating the prioritization process for a chemical, and risk evaluations must be
589 completed in 3 - 3.5 years after a chemical is designated “High Priority” (Supporting Information:
590 Section 1; Section 2, Figure S2). As many studies take multiple years to conduct, the current
591 process does not afford EPA enough time to fill critical data gaps and incorporate new
592 information into the risk evaluation. Thus, EPA must identify these gaps *before* prioritization
593 begins. EPA can implement a “pre-prioritization” process to identify and address data needs
594 necessary for comprehensive risk evaluation, as outlined in the January 2017 proposed
595 prioritization framework rule (Supporting Information, Section 3).

596 To implement a pre-prioritization process, the Agency should regularly update a formal
597 list of candidates for risk evaluation and immediately require TSCA section 8 reporting of
598 existing health and safety information when a chemical is added to the list. After evaluating the
599 section 8 submissions and other reasonably available data, EPA should identify data gaps and
600 issue TSCA section 4 test orders to obtain critical missing information for a comprehensive risk
601 evaluation. This proactive process would ensure EPA can identify and fill data gaps before the
602 3.5-year process of risk evaluation is initiated.

603 To accurately assess the health risks posed by chemicals, EPA must ensure the data it
604 requires are comprehensive. To speed data generation, EPA should explicitly define a generic
605 target dataset including physical characteristics, health endpoints, and PESS considerations,
606 with input from scientific and community experts.²⁷ The dataset could identify a range of health
607 effects (e.g., cardiovascular, reproductive and neurodevelopmental toxicity, carcinogenesis)
608 across sensitive life stages (e.g., preconception, fetal and child development, aging), with robust
609 and sensitive assays to identify risk of human health effects. This framework for identifying

610 critical data gaps would guide how EPA can use its statutory authorities for each chemical
611 (based on database completeness).²⁷ EPA’s task is complicated as amended TSCA places the
612 burden on EPA to identify data gaps and obtain data needed to evaluate chemical risks. Thus, a
613 more health-protective version of TSCA would require chemical manufacturers to provide
614 independent and robust health and environmental assessment data to EPA for their chemicals
615 to remain on the market.

616

617 [Systematic Review](#)

618 Systematic review is an approach to ensure all relevant studies are identified and
619 transparently evaluated using pre-specified methods to reduce bias; failure to use appropriate
620 methods can result in exclusion of relevant information concerning exposures and hazards and
621 underestimate risk. Well-established systematic review methods in the field of medicine have
622 been adapted to environmental health.¹⁰¹⁻¹¹³

623

624 [What is required under amended TSCA](#)

625 Amended TSCA requires EPA consider the “weight of the scientific evidence,”¹⁹
626 (Supporting Information, Section 1) when making decisions about chemical risks, which EPA
627 defines in the risk evaluation framework rule as:

628 a systematic review method, applied in a manner suited to the nature of the evidence or
629 decision, that uses a pre-established protocol to comprehensively, objectively,
630 transparently, and consistently identify and evaluate each stream of evidence, including
631 strengths, limitations, and relevance of each study and to integrate evidence as
632 necessary and appropriate based upon strengths, limitations, and relevance.³³

633

634 [How EPA implemented these requirements](#)

635 In 2018, EPA published the *Application of Systematic Review in TSCA Risk Evaluations*
636 (TSCA Method) to “guide the Agency’s selection and review of the scientific studies that are
637 used to inform TSCA chemical risk evaluations.”¹¹⁴ The TSCA Method used in the first 10 risk
638 evaluations, diverged from established best practices for systematic review in every of step of
639 the systematic review process (Supporting Information: Section 1; Section 2, Figure S3).

640 A systematic review method establishes *what* evidence EPA considers and *how* it is
641 evaluated when conducting risk evaluations. Publishing a protocol outlining how the assessment
642 will be conducted in advance is an essential initial step. It ensures judgements regarding the
643 approach to study selection (literature search and screening), study evaluation (internal validity
644 and quality of the body of evidence), evidence synthesis (each evidence stream separately) and
645 evidence integration (across human, animal, *in vitro* streams) are made before reviewing the
646 evidence so knowledge of the results does not bias the risk evaluation. Publication of a *pre-*
647 *specified* protocol is established as a best practice by all valid systematic review methods. EPA
648 explicitly identified a *pre-specified* protocol as an element of TSCA systematic review in its risk
649 evaluation framework rule and in the method documentation. However, EPA did not publish *pre-*
650 *specified* protocols for the first 10 risk evaluations, leaving them open to potential bias.

651 Well-conducted systematic review protocols specify the approach to evaluating risk of
652 bias in studies. Risk of bias is a systematic error or deviation in the true results or inferences of
653 a study due to how a study was designed, conducted, analyzed, or reported that decrease
654 confidence in the results. Risk of bias tools can evaluate exposure and outcome assessment
655 methods in a study. Rather than utilizing an established method for assessing risk of bias,
656 EPA’s TSCA Method introduced a novel method containing three critical issues and was
657 incompatible with the best available science.¹⁰¹⁻¹¹³

658 1. EPA created an arbitrary list of quality metrics and a rating system that excluded
659 studies from further consideration in the risk evaluations when they were rated as
660 “unacceptable for use” due to “serious flaws.”

661 However, the “serious flaws” EPA’s tool identified were not all related to deficits in the
662 underlying research. One of the 14 quality metrics EPA’s tool marked as a “serious flaw” is
663 statistical power (the likelihood a study will detect an effect) (Supporting Information, Section 2,
664 Table S4). Statistical power does not reflect the quality of the research, as a small study can be
665 underpowered but well-conducted and less biased than a larger study.¹¹⁵ In addition, small
666 “underpowered” studies can be combined with other studies in a meta-analysis to derive a more
667 reliable estimate of the relationship between an exposure and an outcome.

668 2. EPA used a quantitative scoring method, assigning arbitrary numerical weights to
669 quality metrics and then summing across metrics to decide whether a study is of
670 “high,” “medium,” or “low” or “unacceptable” quality.

671 Previous evaluations on the use of ‘quality scores’ found a lack an empirical basis for weighting
672 the metrics and that they were not able to distinguish between studies with a high and low risk
673 of bias.^{115, 116} Authoritative guidance on systematic review recommends the use of *qualitative*
674 domain-based ratings without scores combining ratings across domains.¹¹⁷

675 3. EPA’s method included study reporting as one reason for scoring studies
676 “unacceptable for use” across multiple metrics (Metrics 3, 4, 6, 7).¹¹⁸ (Supporting
677 Information, Section 2, Table S4)

678 However, it conflates how well a study is reported with how well the research was conducted.
679 The quality of a study’s reporting does not necessarily indicate the quality of the study or the
680 reliability of its results.¹¹⁹⁻¹²²

681 Implications for public health

682 EPA's failure to pre-specify its methods via published protocols for the first 10 risk
683 evaluations potentially biased its evaluation of the evidence. For example, EPA published both
684 the literature search and screening strategy and the results of the title and abstract screening of
685 the literature for carbon tetrachloride in June 2017. EPA then conducted full text screening,
686 applying then unknown criteria to exclude references it deemed irrelevant. EPA's criteria
687 defining the characteristics of relevant studies were not published until May 2018, almost a year
688 after publication of the searches and initial screening.¹²³ The timing means development of the
689 criteria and the determination of which studies were included and excluded could have been
690 biased by knowledge of the findings of studies found in the literature search.

691 In addition, the EPA's method to assess study quality led to exclusion of relevant
692 evidence from risk evaluations. In the risk evaluation for perchloroethylene, EPA excluded 10
693 studies because of "unacceptable ratings"— 5 based on reporting and 3 due to statistical
694 power.¹²⁴ EPA therefore excluded evidence based on considerations unrelated to real flaws in
695 the underlying research. Failure to include all the relevant evidence could result in
696 underestimation of risk or misidentification of PESS.

697 Recently, the NASEM found EPA's TSCA Method "does not meet the criteria of
698 'comprehensive, workable, objective, and transparent' systematic review method" and found it
699 "to be lacking objectivity at each step, from not using a defined approach to documenting how
700 the problem formulation and protocol are developed. Further examples include inclusion and
701 exclusion criteria that are too broad to identify the evidence, inherent subjectivity within the
702 metrics that make up the evaluation score for study quality."¹¹⁷ The NASEM also found the
703 TSCA Method resulted in "reduced confidence in the findings" of EPA's risk evaluations.¹¹⁷

704

705 Recommendations for Change

706 EPA should follow the NASEM recommendations and implement a systematic review
707 method compatible with empirically-based existing methods and aligns with authoritative
708 definitions of a systematic review, including the Institute of Medicine.¹²⁵ EPA should use a pre-
709 specified protocol outlining scientific methods for every step of each systematic review it
710 conducts, should assess risk of bias in the individual studies without numeric scoring, and
711 should not exclude studies based on study quality or reporting quality.

712 Following the release of the NASEM report in February 2021, EPA announced it would
713 no longer use the TSCA method.^{126, 127} A draft document representing EPA's revised approach
714 to TSCA systematic review was released in December 2021, but the draft failed to address
715 many NASEM recommendations.¹²⁸ In particular, as the draft represents EPA's approach to the
716 23 TSCA risk evaluations currently in progress, EPA still does not satisfy the NASEM
717 recommendation for pre-specified methods to be peer-reviewed and publicly available before a
718 risk evaluation is started and it continues to use a quantitative study quality approach including
719 an arbitrary list of quality metrics and a rating system that excludes studies from further
720 consideration in the risk evaluations. Thus, the current risk evaluations are potentially biased.¹²⁹

721 Our review of the first 10 chemical risk evaluations conducted under amended TSCA
722 finds EPA systematically underestimated risks to human health, particularly to PESS. EPA has
723 completed 10 risk evaluations and, despite flawed approaches, still determined there were
724 unreasonable risks for at least 50%, and upwards of 97%, of the identified conditions of use for
725 all of them. While it is scientifically appropriate for EPA to revisit several aspects of the first 10
726 evaluations, the advantages of making corrections or improvements to the risk evaluations must
727 be balanced against the disadvantages of further delays in issuing risk management rules to
728 address unreasonable risk, which would result in continued harmful exposures. Revisions to the
729 first 10 risk evaluations should prioritize improvements that affect the unreasonable risk
730 determinations or provide a stronger foundation for risk management actions. Failure to remedy

731 shortcomings in the first 10 chemical risk evaluations will result in continued systematic
732 underestimation of risk for chemicals currently and still to be evaluated under amended TSCA.

733 The goals of amended TSCA and EPA policies often aspire to protect health, but their
734 implementation often fails to ensure equitable, socially just safeguards.^{130, 131} Using the
735 recommendations in this paper, EPA could implement amended TSCA to use the best available
736 science and advance its commitment to health equity, address harmful industrial chemicals, and
737 *“take into account the distributional consequences of regulations...to ensure that regulatory*
738 *initiatives appropriately benefit and do not inappropriately burden disadvantaged, vulnerable, or*
739 *marginalized communities.”*¹³²

740

741 **Author Information**

742 Corresponding Author

743 Nicholas Chartres - Program on Reproductive Health and the Environment, Department of
744 Obstetrics, Gynecology and Reproductive Sciences, University of California San Francisco
745 School of Medicine, San Francisco, CA 94143 USA. Email: Nicholas.Chartres@ucsf.edu

746 Authors

747 Swati D.G. Rayasam - Program on Reproductive Health and the Environment, Department of
748 Obstetrics, Gynecology and Reproductive Sciences, University of California San Francisco
749 School of Medicine, San Francisco, CA 94143 USA

750 Patricia D. Koman - Environmental Health Sciences, University of Michigan School of Public
751 Health, Ann Arbor, MI 48109 USA

752 Daniel A. Axelrad - Independent consultant, Washington, DC 20004 USA

753 Tracey J. Woodruff - Program on Reproductive Health and the Environment, Department of
754 Obstetrics, Gynecology and Reproductive Sciences, University of California San Francisco
755 School of Medicine, San Francisco, CA 94143 USA; Environmental Research and Translation

756 for Health, Department of Obstetrics, Gynecology and Reproductive Sciences, University of
757 California San Francisco School of Medicine, San Francisco, CA 94143 USA

758

759 **Notes**

760 The authors declare no competing financial interest.

761

762 **Acknowledgment**

763 The authors gratefully acknowledge the input from Jonathan Kalmuss-Katz. This work was
764 supported by The JPB Foundation (201903-1505), The Tides Foundation (1092-56821), The
765 Marisla Foundation (1-21-028/1), and The Passport Foundation.

766

767 **Supporting Information:** Referenced sections of statutory language of amended TSCA,
768 Supplemental Figures and Tables referenced in text, and selected changes between EPA's
769 proposed and final risk evaluation framework rule.

770

771

772

773

774

775

776

777

778

779

780

781

782 **References**

- 783 1. Smith, J. K., World War II and the Transformation of the American Chemical Industry. In *Science,*
784 *Technology and the Military*, Springer Netherlands: 1988; pp 307-322.
- 785 2. US Environmental Protection Agency, Train Sees New Toxic Substances Law as Preventive
786 Medicine. In 1976.
- 787 3. Council on Environmental Quality, Toxic Substances Strategy Committee Report to the
788 President. In *44 FR 48134*, 1979.
- 789 4. Silbergeld, E. K.; Mandrioli, D.; Cranor, C. F., Regulating chemicals: law, science, and the
790 unbearable burdens of regulation. *Annu Rev Public Health* **2015**, *36*, 175-91.
- 791 5. World Health Organization, *Public health impact of chemicals: knowns and unknowns; 2019 data*
792 *addendum* World Health Organization Chemical Safety and Health Unit: Geneva, Switzerland, 2021.
- 793 6. Nguyen, V. K.; Kahana, A.; Heidt, J.; Polemi, K.; Kvasnicka, J.; Jolliet, O.; Colacino, J. A., A
794 comprehensive analysis of racial disparities in chemical biomarker concentrations in United States
795 women, 1999-2014. *Environ Int* **2020**, *137*, 105496.
- 796 7. Morello-Frosch, R.; Zuk, M.; Jerrett, M.; Shamasunder, B.; Kyle, A. D., Understanding the
797 cumulative impacts of inequalities in environmental health: implications for policy. *Health Aff (Millwood)*
798 **2011**, *30*, (5), 879-87.
- 799 8. Krinsky, S., The unsteady state and inertia of chemical regulation under the US Toxic Substances
800 Control Act. *PLoS Biol* **2017**, *15*, (12), e2002404.
- 801 9. Wilson, M. P.; Schwarzman, M. R., Toward a new U.S. chemicals policy: rebuilding the
802 foundation to advance new science, green chemistry, and environmental health. *Environ Health*
803 *Perspect* **2009**, *117*, (8), 1202-9.
- 804 10. Woodruff, T. J.; Burke, T. A.; Zeise, L., The need for better public health decisions on chemicals
805 released into our environment. *Health Aff (Millwood)* **2011**, *30*, (5), 957-67.
- 806 11. Koman, P. D.; Singla, V.; Lam, J.; Woodruff, T. J., Population susceptibility: A vital consideration
807 in chemical risk evaluation under the Lautenberg Toxic Substances Control Act. *PLoS Biol* **2019**, *17*, (8),
808 e3000372.
- 809 12. Markell, D., An Overview of TSCA, Its History and Key Underlying Assumptions, and Its Place in
810 Environmental Regulation *Washington University Journal of Law & Policy* **2010**, *32*, (1), 333.
- 811 13. Corrosion Proof Fittings v. the Environmental Protection Agency and William K. Reilly. In *US*
812 *Court of Appeals, Fifth Circuit*, US Court of Appeals, Fifth Circuit: 1991.
- 813 14. Shaffer, R. M., Environmental Health Risk Assessment in the Federal Government: A Visual
814 Overview and a Renewed Call for Coordination. *Environ Sci Technol* **2021**, *55*, (16), 10923-10927.
- 815 15. Safe Drinking Water and Toxic Enforcement Act of 1986 (Proposition 65). In *HSC §*
816 *25249.14* California Code of Regulations; Health and Safety Code, 1986.
- 817 16. The President's Cancer Panel, *Reducing Environmental Cancer Risk: What we can do now.*;
818 National Institutes of Health, National Cancer Institute: 2010.
- 819 17. U.S. Government Accountability Office, *Toxic Substances: Report to Congressional Requesters*;
820 2013.
- 821 18. US Environmental Protection Agency, About the TSCA Chemical Substance Inventory.
822 <https://www.epa.gov/tsca-inventory/about-tsca-chemical-substance-inventory>, (July 1, 2022).
- 823 19. US Environmental Protection Agency, Toxic Substances Control Act (TSCA). In Vol. 15 USC ch. 53
824 subch. I §§ 2601–2629.
- 825 20. Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH). In *COM 2003/0644*
826 *Final*, European Union, 2006.
- 827 21. **Food Quality Protection Act (FQPA)**,. In United States, 1996.

- 828 22. US EPA Office of Inspector General, *Improving EPA research programs - Further Efforts Needed*
829 *to Uphold Scientific Integrity Policy at EPA*; Washington, DC, 2020.
- 830 23. Freedhoff, M., *The Promise of TSCA*; 2021.
- 831 24. Shogren, E., EPA scientists found a toxic chemical damages fetal hearts. The Trump White House
832 rewrote their assessment. *Reveal Magazine*, 2020, (July 1, 2022).
- 833 25. Woodruff, T. J.; Zota, A. R.; Schwartz, J. M., Environmental chemicals in pregnant women in the
834 United States: NHANES 2003-2004. *Environ Health Perspect* **2011**, *119*, (6), 878-85.
- 835 26. US Environmental Protection Agency, Chemicals Undergoing Risk Evaluation under TSCA.
836 [https://www.epa.gov/assessing-and-managing-chemicals-under-tsca/chemicals-undergoing-risk-](https://www.epa.gov/assessing-and-managing-chemicals-under-tsca/chemicals-undergoing-risk-evaluation-under-tsca)
837 [evaluation-under-tsca](https://www.epa.gov/assessing-and-managing-chemicals-under-tsca/chemicals-undergoing-risk-evaluation-under-tsca), (July 1, 2022).
- 838 27. Woodruff, T.; Rayasam, S.; Axelrad, D.; Koman, P.; Chartres, N.; Bennett, D.; Birnbaum, L.;
839 Brown, P.; Carignan, C.; Cooper, C.; Cranor, C.; Diamond, M.; Franjevic, S.; Gartner, E.; Hattis, D.; Hauser,
840 R.; Heiger-Bernays, W.; Joglekar, R.; Lam, J.; Levy, J.; MacRoy, P.; Maffini, M.; Marquez, E.; Morello-
841 Frosch, R.; Nachman, K.; Nielsen, G.; Oksas, C.; Panagopoulos Abrahamsson, D.; Patisaul, H.; Patton, S.;
842 Robinson, J.; Rodgers, K.; Rossi, M.; Rudel, R.; Sass, J.; Sathyanarayana, S.; Schettler, T.; Shaffer, R.;
843 Shamasunder, B.; Shepard, P.; Shrader-Frechette, K.; Solomon, G.; Subra, W.; Vandenberg, L.;
844 Varshavsky, J.; White, R.; Zarker, K.; Zeise, L., Setting a Health-Protective, Scientific Agenda for Chemical
845 Policy: Overview and Consensus Statement (In Revision). In 2022.
- 846 28. Mcpartland, J.; Shaffer, R. M.; Fox, M. A.; Nachman, K. E.; Burke, T. A.; Denison, R. A., Charting a
847 Path Forward: Assessing the Science of Chemical Risk Evaluations under the Toxic Substances Control
848 Act in the Context of Recent National Academies Recommendations. *Environmental Health Perspectives*
849 **2022**, *130*, (2).
- 850 29. Varshavsky, J.; Rayasam, S.; Sass, J.; Axelrad, D.; Cranor, C.; Hattis, D.; Hauser, R.; Koman, P.;
851 Marquez, E.; Morello-Frosch, R.; Oksas, C.; Patton, S.; Robinson, J.; Sathyanarayana, S.; Shepard, P.;
852 Woodruff, T., Current practice and recommendations for advancing how human variability and
853 susceptibility are considered in chemical risk assessment (In Revision). In 2022.
- 854 30. Nielsen, G.; Heiger-Bernays, W.; Levy, J.; White, R.; Axelrad, D.; Lam, J.; Chartres, N.;
855 Panagopoulos Abrahamsson, D.; Rayasam, S.; Shaffer, R.; Zeise, L.; Woodruff, T.; Ginsberg, G.,
856 Application of Probabilistic Methods to Address Variability and Uncertainty in Estimating Risks for Non-
857 Cancer Health Effects (In Revision). In *Environmental Health*, 2022.
- 858 31. Safer Chems., Healthy Families v. EPA. In *Federal Reporter 3rd Series*, United States Court of
859 Appeals, 9th Circuit: 2019; Vol. 943.
- 860 32. Environmental Defense Fund, The Court's TSCA decision is a much bigger win for public health
861 than first meets the eye. [https://blogs.edf.org/health/2019/11/15/the-courts-tsca-decision-is-a-much-](https://blogs.edf.org/health/2019/11/15/the-courts-tsca-decision-is-a-much-bigger-win-for-public-health-than-first-meets-the-eye/)
862 [bigger-win-for-public-health-than-first-meets-the-eye/](https://blogs.edf.org/health/2019/11/15/the-courts-tsca-decision-is-a-much-bigger-win-for-public-health-than-first-meets-the-eye/), (July 1, 2022).
- 863 33. US Environmental Protection Agency, Procedures for Chemical Risk Evaluation under the
864 Amended Toxic Substances Control Act (Final). In 2017; Vol. 40 CFR 702.
- 865 34. US Environmental Protection Agency, Problem Formulation of the Risk Evaluation for Carbon
866 Tetrachloride (Methane, Tetrachloro-) CASRN: 56-23-5 In 2018.
- 867 35. National Academies of Sciences Engineering and Medicine, *A Class Approach to Hazard*
868 *Assessment of Organohalogen Flame Retardants*. ; Washington, DC, 2019.
- 869 36. US Environmental Protection Agency, Regulatory Impact Analysis for Phasing Down Production
870 and Consumption of Hydrofluorocarbons (HFCs). In 2021.
- 871 37. US Environmental Protection Agency, Risk Evaluation for 1-Bromopropane (n-Propyl Bromide).
872 In 2020.
- 873 38. US Environmental Protection Agency, Granting Petitions To Add n-Propyl Bromide to the List of
874 Hazardous Air Pollutants. In *Federal Register*: Washington, DC, 2017; Vol. 82, pp 2354-2362.

- 875 39. McElroy, A.; Hyman, M.; Knappe, D., 1,4-Dioxane in drinking water: emerging for 40 years and
876 still unregulated *Current Opinion in Environmental Science & Health* **2019**, *7*, 117-125.
- 877 40. National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health, Hierarchy of Controls.
878 <https://www.cdc.gov/niosh/topics/hierarchy/default.html>, (July 1, 2022).
- 879 41. US Environmental Protection Agency, Pollution Prevention Policy Statement In 1993.
- 880 42. Mohai, P.; Lantz, P. M.; Morenoff, J.; House, J. S.; Mero, R. P., Racial and socioeconomic
881 disparities in residential proximity to polluting industrial facilities: evidence from the Americans'
882 Changing Lives Study. *Am J Public Health* **2009**, *99 Suppl 3*, S649-56.
- 883 43. Houston, D.; Li, W.; Wu, J., Disparities in exposure to automobile and truck traffic and vehicle
884 emissions near the Los Angeles-Long Beach port complex. *Am J Public Health* **2014**, *104*, (1), 156-64.
- 885 44. US Environmental Protection Agency, Draft TSCA Screening Level Approach for Assessing
886 Ambient Air and Water Exposures to Fenceline Communities Version 1.0. In Office of Chemical Safety
887 and Pollution Prevention U.S. Environmental Protection Agency, Ed. 2022.
- 888 45. Association of State Drinking Water Administrators; Association of Metropolitan Water
889 Agencies, 2021-April-20-ASDWA-and-AMWA-Letter-to-OSCPP. In Dr. Michal Freedhoff Acting Assistant
890 Administrator Office of Chemical Safety and Pollution Prevention (OCSPP); U.S. Environmental
891 Protection Agency, Eds. 2021.
- 892 46. Tessum, C. W.; Paolella, D. A.; Chambliss, S. E.; Apte, J. S.; Hill, J. D.; Marshall, J. D., PM 2.5
893 pollutants disproportionately and systemically affect people of color in the United States. *Sci Adv* **2021**, *7*,
894 (18).
- 895 47. McDonald, Y. J.; Jones, N. E., Drinking Water Violations and Environmental Justice in the United
896 States, 2011-2015. *Am J Public Health* **2018**, *108*, (10), 1401-1407.
- 897 48. US Environmental Protection Agency, E.O. 13985 EQUITY ACTION PLAN: U.S. ENVIRONMENTAL
898 PROTECTION AGENCY. In 2022.
- 899 49. US Environmental Protection Agency, Framework for Cumulative Risk Assessment. In Office of
900 Research and Development Center for Public Health and Environmental Assessment (CPHEA) formerly
901 known as the National Center for Environmental Assessment (NCEA), Ed. Washington, DC, 2003; Vol.
902 EPA/600/P-02/001F.
- 903 50. US Environmental Protection Agency, Risk Evaluation for n-Methylpyrrolidone (2-Pyrrolidinone,
904 1-Methyl-) (NMP) CASRN: 872-50-4. In Office of Chemical Safety and Pollution Prevention U.S.
905 Environmental Protection Agency, Ed. 2020.
- 906 51. US Environmental Protection Agency, Risk Evaluation for Cyclic Aliphatic Bromide Cluster
907 (HBDC). In 2020.
- 908 52. US Environmental Protection Agency, Summary of External Peer Review and Public Comments
909 and Disposition for 1,4-Dioxane. In 2021.
- 910 53. National Research Council, Science and Decisions: Advancing Risk Assessment. In 2009.
- 911 54. National Research Council, Phthalates and Cumulative Risk Assessment: The Tasks Ahead. In
912 2008.
- 913 55. Orum, P.; Moore, R.; Roberts, M.; Sánchez, J., *Who's in danger? Race, poverty, and chemical*
914 *disasters: a demographic analysis of chemical disaster vulnerability zones.*; Environmental Justice and
915 Health Alliance for Chemical Policy Reform Coming Clean Center for Effective Government,.; 2014.
- 916 56. Natural Resources Defense Council; UCSF Program on Reproductive Health and the
917 Environment; Milkin Institute School of Public Health, In *Proceedings of the workshop on conducting*
918 *evaluations of evidence that are transparent, timely and lead to health-protective actions.,* 2021; 2021.
- 919 57. Bullard, R.; Mohai, P.; Saha, R.; Wright, B., *Toxic Wastes and Race at Twenty, 1987–2007*; United
920 Church of Christ Justice and Witness Ministries: San Leandro, CA, 2007.
- 921 58. Lerner, S., *Sacrifice Zones: The Front Lines of Toxic Chemical Exposure in the United States*. MIT
922 Press: 2012; p 368.

- 923 59. Ginsberg, G. L., Cadmium Risk Assessment in Relation to Background Risk of Chronic Kidney
924 Disease. *Journal of Toxicology and Environmental Health, Part A* **2012**, *75*, (7), 374-390.
- 925 60. Ginsberg, G. L.; Dietert, R. R.; Sonawane, B. R., Susceptibility Based Upon Chemical Interaction
926 with Disease Processes: Potential Implications for Risk Assessment. *Current Environmental Health*
927 *Reports* **2014**, *1*, (4), 314-324.
- 928 61. Pullen Fedinick, K.; Yiliqi, I.; Lam, Y.; Lennett, D.; Singla, V.; Rotkin-Ellman, M.; Sass, J., A
929 Cumulative Framework for Identifying Overburdened Populations under the Toxic Substances Control
930 Act: Formaldehyde Case Study. *Int J Environ Res Public Health* **2021**, *18*, (11).
- 931 62. US Environmental Protection Agency, EPA Supplementary Guidance for Conducting Health Risk
932 Assessment of Chemical Mixtures. In 2016.
- 933 63. US Environmental Protection Agency, TSCA Science Advisory Committee on Chemicals Meeting
934 Minutes and Final Report No. 2019-03, Peer Review for the United States Environmental Protection
935 Agency (EPA) Draft Risk Evaluation for 1-Bromopropane (1-BP) (SACC Report on 1-BP). In 2019.
- 936 64. US Executive Office of the President, Executive Order on Tackling the Climate Crisis at Home and
937 Abroad § 219. In 2021.
- 938 65. Bennett, D.; Bellinger, D. C.; Birnbaum, L. S.; Bradman, A.; Chen, A.; Cory-Slechta, D. A.; Engel, S.
939 M.; Fallin, M. D.; Halladay, A.; Hauser, R.; Hertz-Picciotto, I.; Kwiatkowski, C. F.; Lanphear, B. P.;
940 Marquez, E.; Marty, M.; McPartland, J.; Newschaffer, C. J.; Payne-Sturges, D.; Patisaul, H. B.; Perera, F.
941 P.; Ritz, B.; Sass, J.; Schantz, S. L.; Webster, T. F.; Whyatt, R. M.; Woodruff, T. J.; Zoeller, R. T.; Anderko,
942 L.; Campbell, C.; Conry, J. A.; DeNicola, N.; Gould, R. M.; Hirtz, D.; Huffling, K.; Landrigan, P. J.; Lavin, A.;
943 Miller, M.; Mitchell, M. A.; Rubin, L.; Schettler, T.; Tran, H. L.; Acosta, A.; Brody, C.; Miller, E.; Miller, P.;
944 Swanson, M.; Witherspoon, N. O.; American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists (ACOG); Child
945 Neurology Society; Endocrine Society; International Neurotoxicology Association; International Society
946 for Children's Health and the Environment; International Society for Environmental Epidemiology;
947 National Council of Asian Pacific Islander Physicians; National Hispanic Medical Association; National
948 Medical Association, Project TENDR: Targeting Environmental Neuro-Developmental Risks The TENDR
949 Consensus Statement. *Environ Health Perspect* **2016**, *124*, (7), A118-22.
- 950 66. Di Renzo, G. C.; Conry, J. A.; Blake, J.; DeFrancesco, M. S.; DeNicola, N.; Martin, J. N.; McCue, K.
951 A.; Richmond, D.; Shah, A.; Sutton, P.; Woodruff, T. J.; van der Poel, S. Z.; Giudice, L. C., International
952 Federation of Gynecology and Obstetrics opinion on reproductive health impacts of exposure to toxic
953 environmental chemicals. *Int J Gynaecol Obstet* **2015**, *131*, (3), 219-25.
- 954 67. American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists, Committee Opinion No. 575: Exposure to
955 toxic environmental agents. *Obstet Gynecol* **2013**, *122*, (4), 931-5.
- 956 68. US Environmental Protection Agency, Procedures for Chemical Risk Evaluation under the
957 Amended Toxic Substances Control Act (Proposed) In 2017.
- 958 69. US Environmental Protection Agency, Final Risk Evaluation for 1,4-Dioxane. In 2020.
- 959 70. Institute of Medicine, To Err is Human: Building a Safer Health System. In 2000.
- 960 71. Shaffer, R. M.; Smith, M. N.; Faustman, E. M., Developing the Regulatory Utility of the
961 Exposome: Mapping Exposures for Risk Assessment through Lifestage Exposome Snapshots (LEnS).
962 *Environmental Health Perspectives* **2017**, *125*, (8), 085003.
- 963 72. Phelan, J.; Link, B., Is Racism a Fundamental Cause of Inequalities in Health? *Annual Review of*
964 *Sociology* **2015**.
- 965 73. Phelan, J. C.; Link, B. G.; Tehranifar, P., Social Conditions as Fundamental Causes of Health
966 Inequalities: Theory, Evidence, and Policy Implications. *Journal of Health and Social Behavior* **2010**, *51*,
967 (1_suppl), S28-S40.
- 968 74. Link, B. G.; Phelan, J., Social conditions as fundamental causes of disease. *J Health Soc Behav*
969 **1995**, *Spec No*, 80-94.

970 75. US Environmental Protection Agency, America's Children and the Environment.
971 <https://www.epa.gov/americaschildrenenvironment>, (July 1, 2022).

972 76. US Environmental Protection Agency, Draft Toxic Substances Control Act Risk Evaluations: 1-
973 Bromopropane. Comment submitted by Swati Rayasam, Science Associate, Program on Reproductive
974 Health and the Environment, University of California, San Francisco. In 2019.

975 77. US Environmental Protection Agency, Integrated Science Assessment (ISA) for Particulate
976 Matter. In Washington, DC, 2019.

977 78. National Research Council, *Exposure Science in the 21st Century: A Vision and a Strategy*;
978 Washington, DC, 2012.

979 79. Sullivan, J.; Croisant, S.; Howarth, M.; Rowe, G. T.; Fernando, H.; Phillips-Savoy, A.; Jackson, D.;
980 Prochaska, J.; Ansari, G. A. S.; Penning, T. M.; Elferink, C.; Community Partner Authors: Louisiana
981 Environmental Action Network, U. H. N., Bayou Interfaith Shared Community Organizing, Dustin Nguyen-
982 Vietnamese Community Partner, Center for Environmental & Economic Justice, and Alabama Fisheries
983 Cooperative Project Community Scientist Author: Wilma Subra, Building and Maintaining a Citizen
984 Science Network With Fishermen and Fishing Communities Post Deepwater Horizon Oil Disaster Using a
985 CBPR Approach. *New Solut* **2018**, *28*, (3), 416-447.

986 80. Eggers, M. J.; Doyle, J. T.; Lefthand, M. J.; Young, S. L.; Moore-Nall, A. L.; Kindness, L.; Medicine,
987 R. O.; Ford, T. E.; Dietrich, E.; Parker, A. E.; Hoover, J. H.; Camper, A. K., Community Engaged Cumulative
988 Risk Assessment of Exposure to Inorganic Well Water Contaminants, Crow Reservation, Montana. *Int J*
989 *Environ Res Public Health* **2018**, *15*, (1).

990 81. Hoover, E., Cultural and health implications of fish advisories in a Native American community.
991 *Ecol Process* **2013**, *2*, (4).

992 82. Community Action to Promote Healthy Environments, *Public Health Action Plan - Improving Air*
993 *Quality & Health in Detroit*; 2017.

994 83. Chiu, W. A.; Axelrad, D. A.; Dalaijamts, C.; Dockins, C.; Shao, K.; Shapiro, A. J.; Paoli, G., Beyond
995 the RfD: Broad Application of a Probabilistic Approach to Improve Chemical Dose-Response Assessments
996 for Noncancer Effects. *Environ Health Perspect* **2018**, *126*, (6), 067009.

997 84. APROBA web: an interactive web application for probabilistic hazard characterization/dose-
998 response assessment. <https://wchiu.shinyapps.io/APROBAweb/>, (July 1, 2022).

999 85. US Environmental Protection Agency, C.I. Pigment Violet 29; Revised Draft Toxic Substances
1000 Control Act (TSCA) Risk Evaluation; Notice of Availability, Letter Peer Review and Public Comment.
1001 Comment submitted by Swati Rayasam et al., Science & Policy Program on Reproductive Health and the
1002 Environment Department of Obstetrics, Gynecology and Reproductive Sciences, University of California,
1003 San Francisco's Program on Reproductive Health and the Environment (UCSF PRHE). In 2020.

1004 86. US Environmental Protection Agency, EPA Scientific Advisory Committee on Chemicals (SACC)
1005 June PV 29 Meeting Transcript. In 2019.

1006 87. US Environmental Protection Agency, PV29 Response to Peer Review + Public Comments. In
1007 2020.

1008 88. Wagner, W. E.; Gold, S. C., Legal obstacles to toxic chemical research. *Science* **2022**, *375*, (6577),
1009 138-141.

1010 89. Zeise, L.; Wilson, R.; Crouch, E. A. C., Use of Acute Toxicity to Estimate Carcinogenic Risk *Risk*
1011 *Analysis* **1984**, *4*.

1012 90. Crouch, E.; Wilson, R.; Zeise, L., Tautology or not tautology? *J Toxicol Environ Health* **1987**, *20*,
1013 (1-2), 1-10.

1014 91. Zeise, L.; Crouch, E. A. C.; Wilson, R., A Possible Relationship Between Toxicity and
1015 Carcinogenicity. *JOURNAL OF THE AMERICAN COLLEGE OF TOXICOLOGY* **1986**, *5*, (2).

- 1016 92. Crouch, E. A. C.; Feller, J.; Fiering, M. B.; Hakanoglu, E.; Wilson, R.; Zeise, L., Health and
1017 Environmental Effects Document: Non-Regulatory and Cost Effective Control of Carcinogenic Hazard. In
1018 Department of Energy, H., and Assessment Division, Office of Energy Research, Ed. 1982.
- 1019 93. Gold, L. S.; Sawyer, C. B.; Magaw, R.; Backman, G. M.; de Veciana, M.; Levinson, R.; Hooper, N.
1020 K.; Havender, W. R.; Bernstein, L.; Peto, R., A carcinogenic potency database of the standardized results
1021 of animal bioassays. *Environ Health Perspect* **1984**, *58*, 9-319.
- 1022 94. US Environmental Protection Agency, Collaborative agreements for computational toxicology
1023 research. In 2022.
- 1024 95. European Commission, Toward precision toxicology: new approach methodologies for chemical
1025 safety. In 2022.
- 1026 96. US Environmental Protection Agency, Transmittal of meeting minutes and final report for the
1027 federal insecticide, fungicide, and rodenticide act, scientific advisory panel (FIFRA SAP) virtual meeting
1028 held on September 15-18, 2020. In 2020.
- 1029 97. Ginsberg, G. L.; Pullen Fedinick, K.; Solomon, G. M.; Elliott, K. C.; Vandenberg, J. J.; Barone, S.;
1030 Bucher, J. R., New Toxicology Tools and the Emerging Paradigm Shift in Environmental Health Decision-
1031 Making. *Environ Health Perspect* **2019**, *127*, (12), 125002.
- 1032 98. Knudsen, T. B.; Fitzpatrick, S. C.; De Abrew, K. N.; Birnbaum, L. S.; Chappelle, A.; Daston, G. P.;
1033 Dolinoy, D. C.; Elder, A.; Euling, S.; Faustman, E. M.; Fedinick, K. P.; Franzosa, J. A.; Haggard, D. E.; Haws,
1034 L.; Kleinstreuer, N. C.; Buck Louis, G. M.; Mendrick, D. L.; Rudel, R.; Saili, K. S.; Schug, T. T.; Tanguay, R. L.;
1035 Turley, A. E.; Wetmore, B. A.; White, K. W.; Zurlinden, T. J., FutureTox IV Workshop Summary: Predictive
1036 Toxicology for Healthy Children. *Toxicol Sci* **2021**, *180*, (2), 198-211.
- 1037 99. Children's Health Protection Advisory Committee, Letter to EPA acting administrator on
1038 protecting children's health under amended TSCA: chemical prioritization. In 2021.
- 1039 100. National Academies of Sciences Engineering and Medicine, New Approach Methods (NAMs) for
1040 Human Health Risk Assessment | Workshop 1. In 2020; pp
1041 [https://www.nationalacademies.org/event/12-09-2021/new-approach-methods-nams-for-human-](https://www.nationalacademies.org/event/12-09-2021/new-approach-methods-nams-for-human-health-risk-assessment-workshop-1)
1042 [health-risk-assessment-workshop-1](https://www.nationalacademies.org/event/12-09-2021/new-approach-methods-nams-for-human-health-risk-assessment-workshop-1).
- 1043 101. Woodruff, T. J.; Sutton, P., The Navigation Guide systematic review methodology: a rigorous and
1044 transparent method for translating environmental health science into better health outcomes. *Environ*
1045 *Health Perspect* **2014**, *122*, (10), 1007-14.
- 1046 102. National Toxicology Program, Handbook for Conducting a Literature-Based Health Assessment,
1047 Using OHAT Approach for Systematic Review and Evidence Integration. In Office of Health Assessment
1048 and Translation, Ed. National Institute of Environmental Health Sciences: 2015.
- 1049 103. National Academies of Sciences Engineering and Medicine, Application of Systematic Review
1050 Methods in an Overall Strategy for Evaluating Low-Dose Toxicity from Endocrine Active Chemicals. In
1051 2017.
- 1052 104. National Research Council, Review of EPA's Integrated Risk Information System (IRIS) Process. In
1053 2014.
- 1054 105. National Academies of Sciences Engineering and Medicine, Progress Toward Transforming the
1055 Integrated Risk Information System (IRIS) Program: A 2018 Evaluation. In National Academies Press:
1056 Washington, DC, 2018.
- 1057 106. Lam, J.; Sutton, P.; Kalkbrenner, A.; Windham, G.; Halladay, A.; Koustas, E.; Lawler, C.; Davidson,
1058 L.; Daniels, N.; Newschaffer, C.; Woodruff, T., A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis of Multiple
1059 Airborne Pollutants and Autism Spectrum Disorder. *PLoS One* **2016**, *11*, (9), e0161851.
- 1060 107. Koustas, E.; Lam, J.; Sutton, P.; Johnson, P. I.; Atchley, D. S.; Sen, S.; Robinson, K. A.; Axelrad, D.
1061 A.; Woodruff, T. J., The Navigation Guide - evidence-based medicine meets environmental health:
1062 systematic review of nonhuman evidence for PFOA effects on fetal growth. *Environ Health Perspect*
1063 **2014**, *122*, (10), 1015-27.

1064 108. Johnson, P. I.; Sutton, P.; Atchley, D. S.; Koustas, E.; Lam, J.; Sen, S.; Robinson, K. A.; Axelrad, D.
1065 A.; Woodruff, T. J., The Navigation Guide - evidence-based medicine meets environmental health:
1066 systematic review of human evidence for PFOA effects on fetal growth. *Environ Health Perspect* **2014**,
1067 *122*, (10), 1028-39.

1068 109. Lam, J.; Koustas, E.; Sutton, P.; Johnson, P. I.; Atchley, D. S.; Sen, S.; Robinson, K. A.; Axelrad, D.
1069 A.; Woodruff, T. J., The Navigation Guide - evidence-based medicine meets environmental health:
1070 integration of animal and human evidence for PFOA effects on fetal growth. *Environ Health Perspect*
1071 **2014**, *122*, (10), 1040-51.

1072 110. Vesterinen, H. M.; Johnson, P. I.; Atchley, D. S.; Sutton, P.; Lam, J.; Zlatnik, M. G.; Sen, S.;
1073 Woodruff, T. J., Fetal growth and maternal glomerular filtration rate: a systematic review. *J Matern Fetal*
1074 *Neonatal Med* **2015**, *28*, (18), 2176-81.

1075 111. Lam, J.; Koustas, E.; Sutton, P.; Padula, A. M.; Cabana, M. D.; Vesterinen, H.; Griffiths, C.; Dickie,
1076 M.; Daniels, N.; Whitaker, E.; Woodruff, T. J., Exposure to formaldehyde and asthma outcomes: A
1077 systematic review, meta-analysis, and economic assessment. *PLoS One* **2021**, *16*, (3), e0248258.

1078 112. Lam, J.; Lanphear, B. P.; Bellinger, D.; Axelrad, D. A.; McPartland, J.; Sutton, P.; Davidson, L.;
1079 Daniels, N.; Sen, S.; Woodruff, T. J., Developmental PBDE Exposure and IQ/ADHD in Childhood: A
1080 Systematic Review and Meta-analysis. *Environ Health Perspect* **2017**, *125*, (8), 086001.

1081 113. Johnson, P. I.; Koustas, E.; Vesterinen, H. M.; Sutton, P.; Atchley, D. S.; Kim, A. N.; Campbell, M.;
1082 Donald, J. M.; Sen, S.; Bero, L.; Zeise, L.; Woodruff, T. J., Application of the Navigation Guide systematic
1083 review methodology to the evidence for developmental and reproductive toxicity of triclosan. *Environ*
1084 *Int* **2016**, *92-93*, 716-28.

1085 114. US Environmental Protection Agency, *Application of Systematic Review in TSCA Risk Evaluations*;
1086 2018.

1087 115. Higgins, J.; Green, S.; Cochrane, C., *Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions*.
1088 In Wiley-Blackwell: Chichester, England and Hoboken, NJ 2008.

1089 116. Jüni, P.; Witschi, A.; Bloch, R.; Egger, M., The hazards of scoring the quality of clinical trials for
1090 meta-analysis. *JAMA* **1999**, *282*, (11), 1054-60.

1091 117. National Academies of Sciences Engineering and Medicine, *The Use of Systematic Review in*
1092 *EPA's Toxic Substances Control Act Risk Evaluations*; Washington,DC, 2021.

1093 118. von Elm, E.; Altman, D. G.; Egger, M.; Pocock, S. J.; Gøtzsche, P. C.; Vandenbroucke, J. P.;
1094 Initiative, S., The Strengthening the Reporting of Observational Studies in Epidemiology (STROBE)
1095 statement: guidelines for reporting observational studies. *J Clin Epidemiol* **2008**, *61*, (4), 344-9.

1096 119. The Cochrane Collaborative, *Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions*. In
1097 Higgins, J.; Thomas, J.; Chandler, J.; Cumpston, M.; Li, T.; Page, M.; Welch, V., Eds. 2021.

1098 120. Devereaux, P. J.; Choi, P. T.; El-Dika, S.; Bhandari, M.; Montori, V. M.; Schünemann, H. J.; Garg, A.
1099 X.; Busse, J. W.; Heels-Ansdell, D.; Ghali, W. A.; Manns, B. J.; Guyatt, G. H., An observational study found
1100 that authors of randomized controlled trials frequently use concealment of randomization and blinding,
1101 despite the failure to report these methods. *J Clin Epidemiol* **2004**, *57*, (12), 1232-6.

1102 121. Guyatt, G.; Oxman, A. D.; Akl, E. A.; Kunz, R.; Vist, G.; Brozek, J.; Norris, S.; Falck-Ytter, Y.;
1103 Glasziou, P.; DeBeer, H.; Jaeschke, R.; Rind, D.; Meerpohl, J.; Dahm, P.; Schünemann, H. J., GRADE
1104 guidelines: 1. Introduction-GRADE evidence profiles and summary of findings tables. *J Clin Epidemiol*
1105 **2011**, *64*, (4), 383-94.

1106 122. Soares, H. P.; Daniels, S.; Kumar, A.; Clarke, M.; Scott, C.; Swann, S.; Djulbegovic, B.; Group, R. T.
1107 O., Bad reporting does not mean bad methods for randomised trials: observational study of randomised
1108 controlled trials performed by the Radiation Therapy Oncology Group. *BMJ* **2004**, *328*, (7430), 22-4.

1109 123. US Environmental Protection Agency, *Strategy for Conducting Literature Searches for Carbon*
1110 *Tetrachloride (CCL4): Supplemental Document to the TSCA Scope Document*. In 2017.

1111 124. US Environmental Protection Agency, Final Risk Evaluation for Perchloroethylene – Systematic
1112 Review Supplemental File:Data Quality Evaluation of Human Health Hazard Studies – Epidemiological
1113 Studies. In 2020.

1114 125. Institute of Medicine, Finding What Works in Health Care: Standards for Systematic Reviews. In
1115 2011.

1116 126. US Environmental Protection Agency, EPA Commits to Strengthening Science Used in Chemical
1117 Risk Evaluations In 2021.

1118 127. Rizzuto, P., EPA Dumps Trump-Era Chemical Analysis Approach After Rebuke. *Bloomberg Law*,
1119 2021, (July 1, 2022).

1120 128. US Environmental Protection Agency, Draft Systematic Review Protocol Supporting TSCA Risk
1121 Evaluations for Chemical Substances In 2021.

1122 129. US Environmental Protection Agency, Comment submitted by University of California, San
1123 Francisco Program on Reproductive Health and the Environment (UCSF PRHE) In 2022.

1124 130. Morello-Frosch, R.; Cushing, L. J.; Jesdale, B. M.; Schwartz, J. M.; Guo, W.; Guo, T.; Wang, M.;
1125 Harwani, S.; Petropoulou, S. E.; Duong, W.; Park, J. S.; Petreas, M.; Gajek, R.; Alvaran, J.; She, J.; Dobraca,
1126 D.; Das, R.; Woodruff, T. J., Environmental Chemicals in an Urban Population of Pregnant Women and
1127 Their Newborns from San Francisco. *Environ Sci Technol* **2016**, *50*, (22), 12464-12472.

1128 131. Schulz, A. J.; Mentz, G. B.; Sampson, N.; Ward, M.; Anderson, R.; de Majo, R.; Israel, B. A.; Lewis,
1129 T. C.; Wilkins, D., RACE AND THE DISTRIBUTION OF SOCIAL AND PHYSICAL ENVIRONMENTAL RISK: A Case
1130 Example from the Detroit Metropolitan Area. *Du Bois Rev* **2016**, *13*, (2), 285-304.

1131 132. US Executive Office of the President, Presidential Memorandum, Modernizing Regulatory
1132 Review, § 2(b)(i). In 2021.

1133